

Results from the survey showed that total labor input on marginal, small, and large rice farms was 130, 151, and 108 d/ha, respectively, of which 3.4% for marginal, 4% for small, and 14% for large farms was hired labor (see table). Women consistently contribute more labor than men across farms and in all operations except land preparation.

Women's contribution as a percentage share of total labor input was highest (83%) on small farms, followed by marginal farms (68%) and large farms (55%). Women, particularly from low-income rice farming families, are involved in almost all the rice operations except plowing, although they do help men make embankments and level soil. In land preparation, female laborers from marginal farms contributed 45% and from small farms, 41.4%. Those from large farms contributed 38.7%.

More than 70% of the rice cultivated is sown by physical transplanting with family rather than hired labor mostly supplying the labor. Female workers contributed 57.2% of the total labor for transplanting on marginal farms, 60.8% on small farms, and 57.6% on large farms. The extent of hiring labor for

marginal, small, and large farms was 18.6%, 43.2%, and 29.5%, respectively. Only female laborers were hired on all farms because, according to the employers, they are more efficient than men for this task.

Interculture operations, mainly weeding, were generally performed jointly by male and female workers, although females' contribution was highest (63%) on the marginal farms. Weeding is done in August, which is the time that female family members enrolled in school are on vacation, and they provide the required additional labor in this activity.

Among the different operations, the labor contribution of female workers was highest (more than 70%) in postharvest activities (threshing, winnowing, drying, and hauling). Female workers contribute more labor in postharvest because rice harvesting and postharvest activities must be finished quickly so that farmers may use the residual soil moisture for the following wheat crop. Farmers usually hire women laborers from poor and landless families. Forty-three percent of the labor input for harvesting rice for all farms was hired, 77% of which was supplied by female workers.

Despite the significant contributions of women, they received lower wages than did men for the same tasks.

Female family members in Kangra District contribute significantly to almost all rice production tasks and provide the bulk of unpaid family labor operations. Female workers contribute a higher percentage to total labor input on marginal and small farms than on large farms.

Because female family members provide most of the labor in rice, they should be trained on improved cultural practices in production. In-depth studies should be done to better understand women's traditional practices in postharvest methods as well as their knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions about rice seed selection, management, and storage.

Women should be direct recipients of extension services in the community. Innovative participatory methods of imparting improved technologies should be designed, taking into consideration women's levels of education and household responsibilities. ■

Education and communication

Knowledge gap on agrochemical use in rice farming

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Inappropriate use of agrochemicals has become a major problem in rice farming. Training and extension programs are often conducted to educate village extension workers (VEWs) and farmers on the correct use of agrochemicals.

A study was conducted in Matara District of Sri Lanka to estimate the knowledge gap between VEWs and

farmers for six practices involving agrochemicals: seed treatment, weed control, fertilizer application, insect pest control, disease control, and precautionary techniques. Standard recommendations were used to determine the main knowledge elements for the practices. For example, elements for fertilizer application were dilution rate, dose, application frequency, timing, and method of application. A scoring procedure was applied

Differences in knowledge levels between village extension workers (VEWs) and farmers.^a Matara District, Sri Lanka.

Practice	Standard score for recommendation	Av score		t value between		
		Village extension workers (n=25)	Farmers (n=50)	Standard recommendation and VEWs	Standard recommendation and farmers	VEVs and farmers
Seed treatment	3	2.4	1.18	5.2***	18.3***	5.65***
Weed control	6	3.68	2.28	18.4***	26.2***	2.50*
Fertilizer application	5	3.64	2.82	14.1***	25.5***	3.92***
Disease control	4	2.44	1.66	13.4***	19.9***	2.71***
Pest control	4	2.96	1.92	12.8***	18.3***	4.74**
Precautionary techniques	6	4.04	3.06	16.0***	22.3***	3.86***

, **, * = significant at 5%, 1%, and 0.1% level, respectively.

to the elements to give each a standard score. A questionnaire was developed to test the knowledge of VEWs and farmers.

The field investigation was conducted during 1992-93 maha (wet) season. Twenty-five VEWs and 50 rice farmers were randomly selected for the survey. An average score for each practice was

calculated separately for VEWs and farmers (see table).

Standard recommendation scores and those of VEWs and farmers were significantly different for all the practices tested. Knowledge levels between VEWs and farmers also show highly significant differences for four practices. This

evidence reveals a knowledge gap between standard recommendations and VEWs' knowledge level and between VEWs' and farmers' knowledge level. VEWs would benefit from intensive training programs on agrochemical use, and farmers from effective extension techniques to disseminate this information. ■

Research methodology

Path analysis of focus expansion in rice sheath blight

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The effects of four factors on focus expansion in sheath blight were studied in the field: N supply, leaf wetness, contact frequency, and inoculum source characteristics. Experiments were conducted during the 1992-93 wet season (WS) and dry season (DS) at IRRI using IR72 and a 20- × 20-cm spacing. Both experiments were laid out in a split-plot design with eight replications.

Main plots consisted of three N input levels applied as urea: 0, 80, and 120 kg N/ha. Subplots comprised hills spaced at 15 × 15 cm, with the central source hill representing the inoculum source. Five subplot treatments were represented by different structures of the inoculum source resulting from different inoculum amounts and positioning: 5 g or 15 g of inoculum, inoculum placed at the upper or the lower layer of the plant canopy, and a noninoculated control. The inoculum consisted of a 5:1 rice grain/hull mixture colonized by an isolate of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn belonging to anastomosis group 1. The source plants were inoculated during the maximum tillering stage.

The area of a focus (a) was assessed as the maximum distance in cm between lesions along rows (length of focus, l) and across rows (width of focus, w) on both sides of the source. It was computed as: $a = \pi(l \times w)/4$. Assessments were made at weekly intervals after inoculation.

Path diagram of the effects of nitrogen content in the leaves (N), area under leaf-to-leaf and leaf-to-sheath contact progress curve (C), area under leaf wetness progress curve (W), initial sheath blight severity on the lower layer (L), and initial sheath blight severity on the upper layer (U) of the source plant on the log-transformed mean rate of focus expansion (F) (see table).

Explanatory variables used in path analysis.

Variable	Description	Unit
N	Area under the progress curve of the N content in the leaves.	% day
W	Overall wetness of the canopy throughout the cropping season (product of mean leaf wetness rating and mean daily rainfall during the cropping season).	-
C	Area under the progress curve of the number of leaf-to-leaf and leaf-to-sheath contacts.	% day
L	Initial sheath blight severity on the lower layer of the source plant.	%
U	Initial sheath blight severity on the upper layer of the source plant.	%